

Circularly Polarized Conical Array for ADS-B Applications in LEO Satellites

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Abstract—This paper presents the design of a dual-layer conical antenna array tailored for Automatic Dependent Surveillance-Broadcast (ADS-B) applications intended for integration into Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites. The proposed antenna system comprises two vertically stacked layers, each comprising six magneto-electric dipole antennas arranged in a circular configuration. Each antenna element covers a sector of $\pm 30^\circ$ in azimuth, providing comprehensive coverage for real-time aircraft tracking over wide geographical regions. The antennas in the upper layer are positioned slightly farther apart due to the conical geometry, optimizing the radiation pattern and minimizing mutual coupling between layers. The array operates within the L-band spectrum (960–1164 MHz), making it suitable for ADS-B communication in remote areas with limited ground station coverage, such as oceans and deserts.

Index Terms—ADS-B, LEO, conical antenna array, magneto-electric dipoles, azimuth coverage, air traffic surveillance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing reliance on satellite-based systems for aeronautical and communication applications has driven the development of innovative antenna technologies. LEO satellites, with their low latency, high throughput and ability to support diverse payloads, are a key platform for applications of air traffic management that enable accurate, real-time tracking of aircrafts, such as Automatic Dependent Surveillance-Broadcast (ADS-B) and L-band Digital Aeronautical Communication Systems (LDACS) [1], [2]. As Eurocontrol states [3], its objective is to optimize aircraft monitoring using a mix of ground-based and space-based ADS-B systems. With the demand for seamless air traffic control in remote regions like oceans and deserts growing, there is a need for efficient, wideband, and reconfigurable antenna systems that can be integrated into satellites [4], [5] in a constellation such as Starlink or Iridium NEXT. Several studies have proposed antennas for ADS-B applications, focusing on microstrip patches and cavity-backed designs to enhance bandwidth and polarization capabilities [6], [7]. These designs often involve magneto-electric dipoles, known for their low profile, wide bandwidth, and polarization flexibility [8]. Recent advancements include crossed dipoles within a cylindrical or conical array configuration, which enhances radiation pattern control and facilitates circular polarization.

This work proposes a magneto-electric dipole array optimized for ADS-B and LDACS applications in LEO satellite platforms. Building on previous designs of cavity-backed and

Fig. 1. Front view of the antenna array simulated in CST, showing the dimensions and the ports with their corresponding numeration indicated in brackets.

TABLE I
DIMENSIONS OF THE CONE AND ARRAY ELEMENTS (UNITS: MM)

A	B	H	c	d	r
510	90	366	32.4	1	30.3

Fig. 2. Perspective view of the array in CST, with dimensions.

conical arrays, this approach combines the advantages of cylindrical and truncated-cone structures, enabling full azimuth coverage. The proposed antenna system's design and simulation demonstrate its potential for next-generation satellite communication networks.

II. ARRAY DESCRIPTION

The proposed antenna array is designed for Automatic Dependent Surveillance-Broadcast (ADS-B) applications, intended for deployment in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites.

Fig. 3. Reflection coefficient for the antenna array across the operational frequency band (960–1164 MHz).

The array consists of two vertically stacked layers forming a conical structure (see Figs. 1 and 2). Each layer comprises six magneto-electric dipole antennas, uniformly distributed in a circular arrangement. This configuration ensures full 360-degree azimuth coverage, with each antenna covering a sector of $\pm 30^\circ$. The conical structure of the array, due to its inclination of 60° respect to the horizon, introduces a slight variation in the positioning of the antennas between the two layers. The upper layer is positioned at a wider radius, which provides better isolation between the elements in the two layers, reducing mutual coupling. This design choice also optimizes the beamforming characteristics, allowing the antennas to focus their radiation within their assigned sectors. The vertical separation between the layers is chosen to be $\lambda/2$ in a straight line between the centers of the radiators (see Fig. 2) to balance compactness with performance while maintaining stable radiation patterns. The horizontal separation of the radiators in the first layer is also $\lambda/2$, and $3\lambda/4$ in the top layer. The apex of the truncated cone is oriented towards the Earth, with each antenna element specifically designed to cover a distinct sector of the Earth’s surface. This orientation ensures that the array maximizes coverage over the Earth as the satellite moves in its orbit, mainly focusing on remote areas where ground-based ADS-B stations are sparse.

Each antenna element in the array is a magneto-electric dipole designed to operate in the L-band (960–1164 MHz) spectrum, ensuring compatibility with ADS-B communication requirements. The antenna unit cell design and configuration are based on the foundational work presented in [9]. Nonetheless, the original implementation left room for improvement, particularly regarding the directivity along the elevation axis to meet the stringent demands of the SATERA project [10]. Additional radiating layers have been incorporated along the z -axis to enhance performance. This adjustment addresses critical design challenges and moves the antenna closer to fulfilling the project’s technical objectives. The dipoles, equally, are configured to achieve circular polarization, which is crucial for reducing polarization mismatches due to the Faraday Rotation

Fig. 4. Isolation between antenna elements across the operational band.

of the ionosphere, as well as the satellite’s movement and the various orientations of aircraft transponders [11]. The antennas are fed through coaxial cables, and each dipole is expected to be mounted on a cavity-backed reflector to enhance directivity and reduce back-lobe radiation. However, this aspect requires further investigation to confirm its effectiveness. In the meantime, the dual-layer design provides flexibility in beam steering. By adjusting the phase and amplitude of the signals at each feed point via a Software Defined Radio (SDR) system, it is possible to dynamically reconfigure the radiation pattern, allowing for enhanced control and adaptability in various operational scenarios. Thus, the feed network has not been physically implemented, and the results are based on simulations using the combined output from CST. Each antenna is fed independently, allowing for potential fine control over the beam direction and polarization. Impedance matching has been optimized in the simulations to ensure minimal reflection loss across the operational bandwidth, providing efficient power transfer between the hypothetical feed network and the antenna elements.

III. SIMULATED RESULTS

The simulated results demonstrate the effectiveness of the dual-layer conical array in terms of reflection coefficients, isolation, and radiation patterns. As shown in Fig. 3, the reflection coefficient for each antenna of the array remains below -10 dB across a wide frequency range (960–1164 MHz), which is the operational band for ADS-B. This indicates efficient impedance matching and minimal power loss due to reflection. The results confirm that the top and bottom layers are well-optimized to ensure the maximum power transmission to the array elements.

The isolation between the antenna elements, depicted in Fig. 4, is mostly below -15 dB across a significant portion of the operational band. While some values exceed -15 dB at specific frequencies, the isolation is generally sufficient to minimize mutual coupling between elements, allowing the individual sectors to operate with relatively low interference. The radiation pattern for the vertical array of one sector (ports

Fig. 5. Radiation pattern of one vertical sector for $\phi = 90^\circ$ at 1090 MHz showing strong directional performance in the azimuthal plane. The maximum directivity is 9.56 dBi.

Fig. 6. Radiation pattern of one vertical sector for $\theta = 120^\circ$ at 1090 MHz demonstrating the elevation performance of the antenna array.

1, 2, 13, and 14) is shown in Figs. 5 and 6, highlighting the strong directional performance of the antenna system and the high directivity (9.56 dBi) achieved for one sector. The pattern for $\phi = 90^\circ$ (Fig. 5) shows a well-defined main lobe, ensuring focused reception in the azimuthal plane. In contrast, the pattern for $\theta = 120^\circ$ (Fig. 6) demonstrates the expected performance in the elevation plane for proper communication with aircraft. These simulated results serve as a solid starting point for future experimental tests, suggesting that the conical geometry could enhance beam steering capabilities across both layers, offering promising coverage in both azimuth and elevation.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The dual-layer conical array shows significant advantages over planar designs, particularly in coverage and isolation. Using magneto-electric dipoles ensures wideband operation

with circular polarization, which is ideal for ADS-B in LEO satellites. The antenna adaptation provides sufficient bandwidth to cover additional aeronautical bands in the future. Although the current results are based on simulations and the feed network is yet to be implemented, the performance is promising. Future work will focus on physical validation and further optimization to improve isolation and beam steering capabilities.

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